

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_type1_c_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:15:20 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	9.921	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.1514	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...0x_type1_c_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:15:20 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	4.105	μm	
Min:	-2.379	μm	
Max:	1.727	μm	
Size:	271177	digits	
Spacing:	0.01514	nm	
NM-points ratio:	4.317 % (388554 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:15:20 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	4.105	μm	
Size:	271177	digits	
Spacing:	0.01514	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.6515	μm	
Ssk	-0.3959		
Sku	3.419		
Sp	1.723	μm	
Sv	2.383	μm	
Sz	4.105	μm	
Sa	0.5053	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	13.96	%	
Smc	0.8348	μm	
Sxp	1.495	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	22.81	μm	
Str	0.4050		
Std	39.25	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.1508		
Sdr	1.103	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.02273	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	0.8575	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.02273	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.5495	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	0.7635	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.09402	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	2.579	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.5821	µm
Mean density of furrows	3574	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	44.99	°
Second direction	36.76	°
Third direction	180.0	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	50.66	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

